

Visualising Overlooked Syntactic Alternatives in the Greek New Testament

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Paper presented by Tony Jurg (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam / ETCBC).¹

I am honoured to present at this year's IOSOT conference the research I have been developing over the past years. As the title suggests, this paper addresses the visualization of syntactic ambiguity in the Greek New Testament. Such a topic is wide-ranging and touches on many dimensions, but within the time available I will necessarily focus on selected aspects.

Over the next twenty minutes, I will begin by situating the project in its broader context, then highlight several key results, and finally conclude with some critical observations and forward-looking proposals for further research.

¹ ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0343-1346>. Academia: <https://vu-nl.academia.edu/TonyJurg>.

At last year’s SBL International Meeting, we introduced a digitally annotated edition of the Greek New Testament. Developed jointly by the Eep Talstra Centre for Bible and Computer (ETCBC)² at the VU Amsterdam and the Center of Biblical Languages and Computing (CBLC) at Andrews University (Berrien Springs, Michigan),³ this project transformed the Nestle 1904 (7th ed.) into a constituency-parsed, syntactically annotated dataset.⁴

While certainly not the first digital annotated edition of the GNT, its significance lies in bringing the New Testament into the same Text-Fabric ecosystem,⁵ which was already available for the Old Testament (BHSA).⁶ In that sense, the New Testament has now caught up. Our dataset was deliberately designed to mirror the BHSA in both taxonomic structure and user experience. With more than fifty features, the dataset offers a comparable depth of annotation, all accessible through Text-Fabric’s versatile API and accompanied by graphical syntax-tree visualizations. The N1904-TF dataset is fully documented and released under a permissive open-source license.⁷

One of Text-Fabric’s core strengths as a research ecosystem for textual analysis lies in its graph-based architecture. This design cleanly separates the surface text from its annotations, ensuring both flexibility and extensibility. Each linguistic unit (whether a word, phrase, clause, or sentence) is represented as a node, identified by a unique integer within the dataset’s namespace.

At the lowest level are the slots, which typically correspond to surface-level elements. These slots are the smallest addressable units in the dataset and, in NLP terminology, are often referred to as tokens. Higher-level structures, such as phrases, clauses, or sentences, are modelled as additional nodes linked to these slots, enabling a hierarchical organisation of annotations. All descriptive information is stored as features, capturing properties like surface text, lemma, part of speech,

² <https://etcbc.nl/>.

³ <https://www.andrews.edu/>.

⁴ The source data for the conversion project was the *macula-greek* version of Eberhard Nestle’s 1904 Greek New Testament, published by the British and Foreign Bible Society. The digital source is available at GitHub: Clear.Bible, “Clear-Bible/macula-greek,” accessed June 25, 2025, <https://github.com/Clear-Bible/macula-greek/tree/main/Nestle1904/>, (licensed under CC BY 4.0). The dataset is based on the print edition: Eberhard Nestle, *H Kainḗ Diathḗkḗ: Novum Testamentum Graece* (New York: Fleming H. Revell Company, 1904), with additional text-critical markers and associated texts drawn from the seventh reprint (1913).

⁵ Text-Fabric is a Python package created by Dirk Roorda. It offers a research ecosystem for analysing and manipulating large textual datasets, especially suited for ancient languages and biblical texts. The software is available at <https://github.com/annotation/text-fabric/>.

⁶ <https://etcbc.github.io/bhsa/>.

⁷ <https://centerblc.github.io/N1904/>.

morphological tags, and syntactic functions. Conceptually, a feature is a key–value mapping that links a node ID to its property value.⁸

The accompanying image, which visualises the graph representation of the first clause of John 1:1, demonstrates how nodes and features interconnect.

This graph-based architecture also enables the seamless integration of annotations. In the initial release of the base dataset, N1904-TF, fifty features were included, spanning multiple linguistic levels: from orthography and lexis to morphology, syntax, and even higher-level semantics such as semantic role labelling. Crucially, the architecture also supports the integration of additional datasets consisting solely of features, which attach new annotations to the existing nodes via their unique identifiers.

For example, we released a supplementary dataset alongside N1904-TF that builds directly on this principle: it adds new annotation layers without altering the underlying text. Its features added further granular annotations, such as declension class, crasis, or discourse details like Synoptic Gospel parallels.⁹ All annotations remain uniformly accessible through the Text-Fabric API, allowing scholars to construct complex queries across arbitrary sections of the data by combining features from both the base dataset and any load-on-demand extensions.

⁸ Dirk Roorda, "Text-Fabric Data Model," accessed June 27, 2025, <https://annotation.github.io/text-fabric/tf/about/datamodel.html>. See also section "Logic: annotated graphs" on the data model of Text Fabric in Dirk Roorda, "Text-fabric: handling Biblical data with IKEA logistics," *HIPHIL Novum* vol 5 issue 2 (2019): 126–135, 128, doi.org/10.7146/hn.v5i2.142740.

⁹ <https://centerblc.github.io/N1904/additions/index.html>.

However, a more significant issue emerged. Review of the output revealed a fundamental limitation: a bare “forest” of alternative trees could illustrate the range of possible outcomes but offered little insight into the underlying reasons. This limitation was already present when working with the disambiguated morphological tags, but it became even more acute once morphological ambiguity was included. It came to a point where the number of parallel syntax trees literally exploded, until it was impossible to see the forest for the trees.

This prompted a shift in perspective: rather than beginning with the effects, an ever-expanding forest of syntax trees, why not return to the underlying cause? What if the first step were to focus on morphological ambiguity itself, integrating it into Text-Fabric, and then developing diagnostic features to detect, visualize, and even quantify its impact on phrase and clause structure? Such an approach promised far clearer insight than attempting to sift through an overwhelming array of competing parses of full sentences.

This refocusing placed morphology at the centre of the project. To generate all possible morphological parses for each wordform, I selected Morpheus, a tool noted for its broad dialectical coverage and established reputation.¹³ Its development reflects decades of work by Gregory Crane and the Perseus Project in advancing accessible computational resources for classical languages. The parser uses a rule-based system based upon extensive lexical tables, encompassing “40,000 stems, 13,000 endings, and 2,500 irregular forms.”¹⁴

¹³ <https://github.com/PerseusDL/morpheus/blob/master/doc/morpheus.html>.

¹⁴ Gregory Crane, “Generating and Parsing Classical Greek,” *Literary and Linguistic Computing*, Vol. 6, No. 4, 1991: 241–245, 244. doi:10.1093/lc/6.4.243.

To capture all ambiguity data for each word, I designed an NLP pipeline with reproducibility as a central principle.¹⁵ The system consisted of three distinct main components: a Jupyter Notebook for generating the Text-Fabric features, the Morpheus analyser for producing morphological parses, and a dedicated gateway that linked the two.

The N1904-TF dataset supplied the surface wordforms, which were passed to Morpheus for analysis. Since Morpheus depends on an older software version, I ran it in a virtual machine,¹⁶ accessed through a lightweight API. To bridge the gap between Morpheus and Text-Fabric, which rely on very different taxonomies and data structures, I also developed a dedicated Python package called Morphkit.¹⁷

Morphkit managed all interactions between the two environments by parsing each analytic block produced by Morpheus, delivered as plain-text with fixed-position tab-separated fields, and converting it into structured Python dictionaries suitable for Text-Fabric feature generation. It also ensured data consistency by aligning and mapping property taxonomies.

The Morpheus Addons Dataset

- Contains all Morpheus analyses for each individual word
- Provides direct access to each individual element per analysis
 - morphological properties (e.g., voice, case, gender)
 - philological properties (e.g., stem, ending)
- Summarizes each block with constructed morphological tag
- Aggregates result per lemma (for compactness and comparison)
- Provides statistical and linkage between levels of detail
- Open Source with permissive license (CC-BY)

- Additional analytic features

Executing this NLP pipeline produced a Morpheus-enhanced dataset for N1904-TF. For each token in the base dataset, all morphological details from every Morpheus block were stored in dedicated Text-Fabric features. Because Morpheus can return up to 24 analytic blocks for a single

¹⁵ https://tonyjurg.github.io/Create_morpheus_TF_dataset/.

¹⁶ <https://hub.docker.com/r/perseidsproject/morpheus-api>.

¹⁷ <https://tonyjurg.github.io/morphkit/>.

token, each representing a distinct morphological parse, additional summary features were introduced to group the analyses by lemma. Metadata features were also added to aggregate counts, such as the total number of blocks per token and the number of distinct lemmas. In addition, several experimental diagnostic features were created, one of which will be discussed in more detail later.

Once the Morpheus output was accessible within Text-Fabric, it became necessary to design a method for comparing each morphological parse with the base N1904-TF annotations. To enable this integration, a mapping step was introduced. In N1904-TF, each token is assigned a Robinson-style morphological tag, adapted by Ulrik Sandborg-Petersen and commonly referred to by us as the SP tag.¹⁸ From the grammatical fields in each Morpheus analysis block, the Morphkit derived one or more SP tags, retaining underspecified values where applicable (e.g., multiple possible genders). This produced a compact and directly comparable encoding of core grammatical properties. Ambiguities became immediately apparent once users enabled the summary features displaying both lemmas and SP tags.

The final Morpheus-enhanced dataset comprises just over 1,000 features, with a total size of about 800 MB. To make it practical for research, we divided it into two parts.¹⁹ The lighter part contains metadata, summary features, and analytic features; these are derivative layers designed for quick exploration and broad analysis. The heavier part holds the complete Morpheus output, preserving all analytic blocks and enabling programmatic access to every detail produced by the analyser. This principled division allows researchers to begin with a lightweight dataset and only load the full data when a detailed examination is required.

Including all Morpheus data in Text-Fabric is valuable, but on its own it does not necessarily yield insight. For that reason, I created a set of diagnostic and analytic features. These go beyond simple data storage and provide structured ways to explore ambiguity, identify recurring patterns, and detect potential outliers. Together, these features support both programmatic queries and visual inspection, making the dataset a practical tool for studying morphosyntactic alternatives.

¹⁸ <https://github.com/biblicalhumanities/Nestle1904/blob/master/morph/parsing.txt>.

¹⁹ https://tonyjurg.github.io/N1904addons/loading_the_dataset.html.

Matthew 2:13 – Tag Sequence Permutations

Ἀναχωροσάντων δὲ αὐτῶν, ἰδοὺ ἄγγελος κυρίου φαίνεται κατ' ὄναρ τῷ Ἰωσήφ λέγων Ἐγερθεὶς παράλαβε τὸ παιδίον καὶ τὴν μητέρα αὐτοῦ καὶ φέυγε εἰς Αἴγυπτον, καὶ ἴσθι ἐκεῖ ἕως ἂν εἶπω σοὶ· μέλει γάρ Ἡρώδης ζητεῖν τὸ παιδίον τοῦ ἀπολέσαι αὐτό.

One phrase with two words:

Word form	τὸ	παιδίον
N1904-TF	T-ASN (ὁ)	N-ASN (παιδίον)
Morpheus 1	T-ASN/T-NSN/T-VSN (ὁ)	N-ASN/N-NSN/N-VSN (παιδίον)
Morpheus 2		N-ASN/N-NSN/N-VSN (παιδίον)
Morpheus 3		N-ASM (παιδίοσ)

Twelve morphological tag permutations (Cartesian product):

T-ASN + N-ASN	T-ASN + N-NSN	T-ASN + N-VSN	T-ASN + N-ASM
T-NSN + N-ASN	T-NSN + N-NSN	T-NSN + N-VSN	T-NSN + N-ASM
T-VSN + N-ASN	T-VSN + N-NSN	T-VSN + N-VSN	T-VSN + N-ASM

One feature deserves closer attention, as it connects morphological ambiguity with potential shifts in phrase function. The underlying assumption is that a word's morphological form largely determines its role within a phrase. For example, when a wordform could be analysed either as genitive or dative, this ambiguity might signal a functional shift between possession and agency.

Since both the N1904-TF SP tag and the Morpheus parses are available for every token, a Cartesian product can be computed for all items in a phrase. Even a two-token phrase can already yield twelve permutations, each represented by a distinct tag sequence, as shown on the sheet.

Matthew 2:13 – Tag Sequence to Phrase Function

12 permutations:

mapping table

2 attested sequences:

Tag Sequence	Phrase Function
PRT	adv:87/p:10/s:3
N-PRI	s:71/p:21/o:4/adv:3/o:2:1
V-PAM-3S	v:86/vc:14
...	...
T-ASN+N-ASN	o:85/s:13/adv:2
T-NSN+N-NSN	s:94/p:3/o:2/adv:1
...	...
T-NSM+N-NSM+P-2GP	s:95/p:5
PREP+T-QSM+N-GSM	adv:89/p:11/s:1
T-NSN+A-NSN+D-GPM	s:100

Before this step, a mapping table was already prepared. For every unique sequence of morphological tags attested in the N1904-TF dataset, the entire corpus was scanned to determine the observed distribution of phrase functions. These distributions were then stored in a lookup table, linking each morphological tag sequence to the probability distribution of its corresponding phrase roles.

The results of the Cartesian product can then be compared against this lookup table. In the example shown, this yields two distinct attestations: one corresponding to the tag sequence found in N1904-TF for the phrase, and another representing an additional alternative tag sequence. Each attestation is associated with a different probability distribution of phrase functions. This comparison provides the basis for testing how ambiguity might shift phrase function.

Matthew 2:13 – Text-Fabric Phrases

Ἀναχωρησάντων δὲ αὐτῶν, ἰδοὺ ἄγγελος κυρίου φαίνεται κατ’ ὄναρ τῷ Ἰωσήφ λέγων· Ἐγερθεὶς παράλαβε τὸ παιδίον καὶ τὴν μητέρα αὐτοῦ καὶ φεύγε εἰς Αἴγυπτον, καὶ ἰσθὶ ἐκεῖ ἕως ἂν εἰπω σοί· μέλλει γὰρ Ἡρώδης ζητεῖν τὸ παιδίον τοῦ ἀπολέσαι αὐτό.

τὸ παιδίον καὶ τὴν μητέρα αὐτοῦ:

N1904-TF & Morpheus: o:100

τὸ παιδίον:

N1904-TF: T-ASN+N-ASN:o: 85/s: 13/adv: 2
Morpheus: T-NSN+N-NSN:s: 94/p: 3/o: 2/adv: 1

The results are stored in a dedicated set of Text-Fabric features. The baseline feature `ma0_pf_altern` encodes the original (inherent) parse and its associated probability distribution.²⁰ The feature `ma1_pf_altern` contains the details for the first alternative tag sequence, and further alternatives can be added in the same way. When these features are displayed, one can quickly examine the potential impact on phrase function if an alternative tag sequence were adopted. In the example, the alternative sequence suggests a possible functional shift from object to subject.

Of course, such a shift is not necessarily likely. It depends entirely on context, such as the presence of another phrase in the clause pointing the other way. Another important caveat is that these probability distributions are derived solely from the syntactic parsing of the Greek New Testament, which, in NLP terms, is a very small corpus. As a result, many valid tag sequences are unattested, and the distributions that are available often rest on a limited number of observations.

Evaluation of the Morpheus Dataset

Successes:

- Morphological + philological data: available for code access and visualisation
- Phrase-level impact of ambiguity: measurable, explorable, visualisable
- Morpheus ↔ N1904-TF comparison: easy, thanks to sharing morphological tagging scheme

Problems:

- Tagging scheme is morphosyntactic, not purely morphological → built-in complications
- N1904-TF data is disambiguated, causing “false” mismatches vs. Morpheus data

Now let us evaluate the resulting dataset. The Morpheus-enhanced dataset offers a robust foundation for exploring ambiguity across multiple linguistic levels. The pipeline stores all Morpheus analyses for each word in dedicated features, enabling users to trace results from high-level SP tags down to individual analytic blocks in a transparent and accessible manner. This approach preserves the full detail of the original data while enhancing usability. The SP tags have proven effective, summarising the detailed output of Morpheus into a single, familiar N1904-TF tag. Because both systems use the same SP-tag taxonomy, comparisons between Morpheus output

²⁰ See https://tonyjurg.github.io/N1904addons/features/ma%7Bind%7D_pf_altern.html.

and the original N1904-TF annotations became straightforward. In addition, the inclusion of phrase-function features opens new possibilities: by precomputing distributions over phrase functions, word-level ambiguity can be linked directly to higher-level syntactic variation using probabilistic weighting.

However, this integration also revealed areas where the two systems were less compatible; issues that only became apparent through the systematic inclusion of the Morpheus data. Paradoxically, the project's greatest strength also exposed what might be called its Achilles' heel. At a deeper level, the process uncovered previously hidden forms of ambiguity already latent within the N1904-TF dataset. This relates specifically to ambiguity introduced through the disambiguation of grammatically underspecified forms. While the original aim was to surface ambiguity by referencing an external system like Morpheus, the extent of internal ambiguity within the dataset proved unexpectedly high and significantly complicated the analysis.

Let us consider a simple example of a data compatibility issue. Because the N1904-TF dataset assigns exactly one disambiguated morphological tag per token, while Morpheus lists all analyses, direct comparisons can sometimes yield misleading results. The N1904-TF approach selects a single contextually appropriate analysis, thereby implicitly hiding all other possibilities, whereas the Morpheus-enhanced dataset explicitly lists every plausible interpretation. This asymmetry complicates token-level comparisons, as illustrated in the accompanying sheet. Text-Fabric features that rely on direct comparison of morphological properties between Morpheus output and the N1904-TF base are vulnerable to such mismatches, which can silently produce inaccurate or misleading conclusions.

One example involves the indeclinable wordform *Isaak*, which appears in a sentence where its syntactic role is accusative. N1904-TF reflects this by tagging the word accordingly. However, since the wordform itself does not morphologically encode case (being indeclinable), Morpheus does not assign a case value. As a result, any comparison on case between the N1904-TF annotation and the Morpheus output will necessarily fail; not due to a contradiction, but because of incompatible assumptions about what the form itself can encode.

The scale of this type of ambiguity proved greater than expected and significantly affected many of the analyses performed. To quantify the issue, I identified all surface wordforms in the N1904-TF dataset that map to two or more distinct morphological tags. This gave us two striking figures. At the wordform level, nearly 4.5% mapped to multiple tags. At the token level, this number rose to over 17%, primarily due to high-frequency items such as articles and pronouns, which often allow for multiple valid interpretations in terms of gender or case.²¹

However, the inherent ambiguity in the N1904-TF dataset is not limited to underspecification of morphological properties. Each SP tag encodes a range of morphological details, beginning with the Part of Speech (POS). While morphological features such as case or number are intrinsic to the wordform, the POS is a syntactic property that often depends on the surrounding context. As shown in this sheet, certain wordforms are tagged with different POS labels in different contexts, often for good and linguistically valid reasons. In effect, this means that the POS portion of the SP tag is not strictly form-based but phrase-dependent.²² Since the SP tags constructed from Morpheus analyses are context-independent by design, this introduces an additional layer of asymmetry in tag comparison. Although the scale of these mismatches appears smaller than those caused by underspecification, they too can silently produce misleading results and flawed conclusions. This reveals yet another asymmetry between the two datasets.

²¹ https://nbviewer.org/github/tonyjurg/N1904addons/blob/main/docs/use_cases/overview_statistics_on_ambiguity.ipynb.

²² The BHS differentiates between a 'part of speech' and a 'phrase dependent part of speech' feature.

To measure morphological ambiguity in the Morpheus-enhanced dataset, we began by counting how many analytic blocks Morpheus returned for each token. On average, this amounted to about 2.6 analyses per token. The chart illustrates this distribution: most words receive more than one possible analysis, and some yield a surprisingly high number of alternatives.

The next step was to compare these results with the N1904-TF dataset. I focused on the ten most ambiguous forms in N1904-TF and examined how many morphological forms Morpheus reported for those same words. The outcome was striking: Morpheus attested every tag present in N1904-TF, but its tag inventory reached beyond what is represented in the N1904-TF annotations. This suggests that, in the process of disambiguation, N1904-TF may have tacitly collapsed or remapped certain Morpheus tags, thereby reducing the apparent range of ambiguity in the final dataset. Taken together, these findings not only confirm the scale of ambiguity in Morpheus but also expose deeper structural tensions with N1904-TF.

Proposed Way Forward - Principles

Fundamental data changes:

- Distinction between “FormalTag” and “FunctionalTag.”¹
- Explicit coding of morphological underspecification (e.g., X for M/F/N) ²

Next step:

- Shallow parsing taking underspecification into account
- Expand tag-space (include LXX – when tagged using the same syntactic assumptions; pragmatically first only phrase level)

1 Jonathan Robie, “Nestle 1904 Greek New Testament,” <https://github.com/Clear-Bible/macula-greek/tree/main/Nestle1904/nodes>

2 “New Draft Morphological Tags for MorphGNT,” *J. K. Tauber* (blog), February 3, 2018. <https://jktauber.com/2018/02/03/new-draft-morphological-tags-morphgnt>.

Example for τῶν: <https://github.com/morphgnt/ablgnt/blob/3b5cbdf92cb5e9bdb48a48026bcc0a08f885dd2c/86-Jud-morphgnt.txt#L290>

This observation revealed a set of important compatibility challenges: underspecification on the Morpheus side collides with overspecification in N1904-TF. Viewed positively, this challenge is itself a key outcome of the research. It highlights concrete areas where the annotation framework can—and perhaps should!—be improved.

Two fundamental adaptations to the data structure appear to be necessary. The first concerns explicit underspecification. A tagging scheme is needed that distinguishes between an inflected form’s possible values and its chosen reading in context. For example, an ending like -ων could

carry a formal tag GPX to indicate “gender = male/female/none,” in line with by James Tauber’s suggestion.²³ At the same time this should be combined with Jonathan Robie’s distinction between formal and functional tags.²⁴

Another step forward will be to expand the training corpus, since many valid morphological sequences are missing from the relatively small N1904-TF dataset. Without them, the phrase-function model cannot score such cases. Training on a broader Biblical Greek resource, such as a syntactically annotated Septuagint, would extend coverage of plausible tag combinations, reduce the number of unrecognized sequences, and make the probability model more robust. Closely related is the need for underspecification-aware parsing. Lightweight methods should be developed that explicitly respect underspecified forms. A shallow parser, for instance, could allow case or gender values to remain open during evaluation, flagging analyses that are grammatically valid but excluded from N1904-TF due to earlier disambiguation. Combined with an expanded tag-space that incorporates Septuagint data, at least at the phrase level, this approach could reveal valid parses that remain hidden in the current framework.

In practical terms, what does such an implementation look like? The sheet demonstrates this using the particle τῶν. It occurs 1201 times in the N1904-TF dataset, where each instance is tagged specifically as T-GPF, T-GPM, or T-GPN. By contrast, in Morpheus’s summary features it appears indiscriminately as T-GPF/T-GPM/T-GPN. This is a textbook case of underspecification, since the ending ῶν can mark any gender. The problem becomes apparent when the datasets are compared: depending on the query, every instance of τῶν may either disappear from the results or be counted multiple times, inevitably distorting any statistical analysis.

The solution is to codify underspecification explicitly. In the Morpheus data this would mean storing a formal tag that captures the full range of possibilities. In the N1904-TF base data, the disambiguated reading should then be stored separately in a functional tag, while an additional formal tag records the analytic block underlying that reading. This is necessary because Morpheus

²³ “New Draft Morphological Tags for MorphGNT.” *J. K. Tauber* (blog). February 3, 2018. <https://jктаuber.com/2018/02/03/new-draft-morphological-tags-morphgnt>.

Example for τῶν: <https://github.com/morphgnt/sblgnt/blob/3b5cbdf92cb5e9bdb48a48026bcc0a08f885dd2c/86-Jud-morphgnt.txt#L290>.

²⁴ Jonathan Robie, “Nestle 1904 Greek New Testament,” <https://github.com/Clear-Bible/macula-greek/tree/main/Nestle1904/nodes>.

can return multiple lemma–morph combinations for the same form. Once such codification is in place and combined with the earlier proposal to expand the training set to handle these cases, the door opens to new possibilities for computational biblical research with a level of precision not achievable in current implementations.

The QR codes on this sheet link you directly to the main GitHub repositories: one for the N1904-TF dataset, and another for the supplementary dataset containing the Morpheus-enhanced dataset. I invite you to explore the data, examine the features, and consider how they might support your own research.

Thank you for your attention.

GitHub repositories

- N1904-TF: <https://centerblc.github.io/N1904/>.
- N1904Addons: <https://tonyjurg.github.io/N1904addons/>.